

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE FUNCTIONAL TASKS OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

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Abstract: the state management system of horses and girls has a cratological essence (state significance) as it is an active subject of socio-political existence. When the new state administration system is being formed, the social and political activity of citizens, the role of democratic values in the decision-making is of incomparable importance.

Key words: mandatory function, cratological point of view, gender equality, political culture, political party

Mandatory functions of the state administration system and voluntary functions of women are dialectically related to each other according to their substantial importance, origin and impact on socio-political existence. If women are forced to take on the functions of the public administration system as a responsible employee, leader, member of the organization (then women are responsible for performing the mandatory functions of the public administration system), and as public members and activists, they also bring their voluntary functions into the operation of the administration system. . Mandatory functions apply to more responsible women, and voluntary functions to public, active women. However, although mandatory functions are not visible, they do not affect the activities of public women, the content and organization of activities. The influence of public women on socio-political existence is determined by their correct understanding of mandatory functions, their contribution to their fulfillment. Therefore, the voluntary functions of public women as an expression of their socio-political activity affect the entire management system and its effective operation. Only a woman who is able to combine her voluntary functions and public activities with the mandatory functions of the state administration system becomes a subject who creates, if necessary, changes, renews or develops the socio-political existence. So, the subject is not just an activity, but a person who actively affects the social and political existence, the state management system.

From the cratological point of view, the socio-political activity of women is also determined by the influence of the state on its place in the political system. In fact, this influence is one of the main criteria indicating that women are an active subject of the public administration system.

Experts say that the role of the state in the political system of society is reflected in the following:

first, the state is the owner of the main means of production, it determines the main directions of development in the interests of all members of society, as well as some citizens;

secondly, the state functions as an association of all citizens;

thirdly, the state has a special apparatus of management and coercion;

fourthly, the state has a wide-ranging system of legal instruments that allows the use of various methods of persuasion and coercion;

fifth, the state is independent;

sixthly, the state is the only organization with full power throughout the country."

Women, as the first subjects of social and political existence, directly affect the above aspects of the state management system, when they are responsible employees, leaders, and indirectly when they are public and active. The source of this influence is determined by the democratic character of the state. If the state is not democratic, the social and political activity of the citizens and all the efforts of the public will be in vain. The democratic character of the state gives the socio-political activity of citizens, including women, a krateological essence, that is, democracy turns women's activity aimed at improving the socio-political existence into a reality that is necessary for development and serves the development of state administration.

The active subject of women in the creation and modernization of social and political existence also affects the prestige of the state in the international arena. Today, when interstate integration is becoming a global reality, the world community and international women's organizations are closely monitoring the issue of women in each country, they are socially monitoring that the states are operating in accordance with democratic principles and fully fulfilling the conditions of international conventions. In such conditions, taking measures aimed at involving women in the management of society and state affairs, ensuring their socio-political subjectivity, cannot fail to acquire a krateological essence.

So, the issue of women does not concern only women, it is a social, political, economic and cultural phenomenon that serves the development of the entire society and the improvement of the state administration system.

Creating the necessary conditions for the realization of women's socio-political aspirations and dreams, their objectification is important for both women and the state administration system. If women have the opportunity to express themselves, express their existing knowledge, experience and potential, and develop them further, the state administration system serves the interests of the general population, proves in practice that it is the power of the people, and improves the political culture of women.

The state, its management system, and social management in general have not left anyone indifferent, because the activities of these institutions are related to the life and destiny of people, people, and the nation. That is why women, especially their socio-politically active part, contribute to solving the problems of socio-political existence.

At the same time, socio-political activity is not "born" in a person ready-made, like Plato's "minemsis". It is a quality that can be formed and inculcated into the human mind, behavior and lifestyle through social educational means. This is often done by the state and its institutions. In scientific literature, it is called "political socialization".

So, objectification, political socialization is an objective necessity for state management and social development.

The relations of women and girls to the socio-political existence encourages them to know and study their social characteristics, which ensure their effective participation in state management. The polyfunctional reality and complexity of socio-political life, state administration, imposes certain demands on the social qualities of women, because the faced object, a person, cannot take on state administration, cannot successfully carry it out, for this

it is not only personal (individual), but also social (social) must have signs and characteristics. In this regard, there is no recommendation in the scientific literature, even in the works of scientists who have specifically studied the problems of women in public administration. It is true that in the candidate's thesis of S.A. Khodzhaeva, candidate of legal sciences, an attempt was made to create a theoretical portrait aimed at determining the socio-legal activity and qualities of women. According to him, social and legal activity of women, their: 1) personal; 2) social; 3) determined by social and legal qualities, it is shown that these signs constitute the portrait of modern active women.

According to the researcher, a politically-legal and socially active woman is a person of 41-66 years of age who actively participates in the life of society, is a member of one of the political parties, and has a humanitarian higher education. She is married, regularly reads legal periodicals, and is interested in the history of the women's movement and contemporary gender issues. He likes correctness, moral qualities, organization and diligence in people. So, a socio-legal woman is a person who is interested in the life of people and times. The researcher studies the life and work of women lawyers in the Soviet era and projects them to the present era, thus creating a portrait of a socio-legal woman. He does not see, does not study, different from the Soviet era, that radical changes have taken place in the women of today, in their consciousness, knowledge, and attitude to social life. As a result, the created portrait becomes a theoretical model far from life and social existence.

The place and status of women in the socio-political existence depends on their political culture.

Doctor of Philosophy, Professor B. T. Toychiev writes that political culture is directly related to the economic system of society, and it is formed under the influence of all spheres of spiritual life. "Political culture," writes B.T. Toychiev, "is the basis of the priority principles for people's political behavior, the value system that ensures its organization to the community."

It organizes social institutions and organizations as priority principles, social norms and ideals for political behavior, ensures their influence on each other, expresses the integral and integrative nature of the political sphere...". At the same time, the scientist emphasizes that political culture is a reality that is related to political consciousness, political knowledge, political experience and integrates other spheres of human activity. So, since there is no pure political reality, politics is essentially related to the life of society and the state, social and political activity should be considered from the point of view of the integrative nature of political culture.

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